

THREE-DIMENSIONAL BRAIDED COMPOSITES FOR REGENERATING ARTICULAR CARTILAGE

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SUMMARY

As articular cartilage in the body is to sustain the joint pressure, its structure is the composite one for effective load bearing. If damaged severely, articular cartilage should be regenerated or replaced by an implant. A scaffold, which mimics native cartilage in the mechanical properties as close as possible, is required for the regeneration. In this study a three-dimensional scaffold was developed using 3D braiding technology and finite element analysis.

Keywords: Articular cartilage, 3-D scaffold, braiding, composite, biodegradable

INTRODUCTION

Articular cartilage, a thin-layered structure in millimeter scale, forms particular tissue at the end of bones (see Figure 1). Since its main role is to support the load at joints, the mechanical properties of the cartilage, featured anisotropy and gradient properties, are most important factor for its well functioning.

Articular cartilage consists of chondrocytes embedded in small spaces called lacuna and extracellular matrix of collagens, proteoglycans and noncollagenous proteins. Chondrocytes make and manipulate a cartilage. If damaged severely, articular cartilage should be regenerated or replaced by an implant; however chondrocytes themselves cannot lay down other matrix and regenerate a cartilage. A scaffold is required that can mimic the natural articular cartilage matrix and cultivate chondrocytes well.

Figure 1. Structure of articular cartilage (Knee)

Recently a composite scaffold that has similar anisotropic mechanical properties to those of natural cartilage was developed using three dimensional woven composite, however its compressive modulus is not matched with natural one [1]. In this study, the braiding technology was used to design three dimensional composite scaffold having similar mechanical properties to the natural one including compressive properties. Furthermore, the mechanical anisotropy and hydraulic permeability were also tailored to match the natural cartilage.

DESIGN METHODOLOGIES

Controlling processing conditions such as braiding angle and yarn orientation, various 3D textile structures can be manufactured by the braiding technology. Furthermore the braiding technology can produce gradient structures in thickness via axial yarns. This gradient structure is essential to ensuring the same order of compressive modulus of braided composites as that of the native articular cartilage without deteriorated tensile modulus.

Finite element analysis enables a specific 3D braided structure to be designed effectively. For the structural analysis, a unit-cell of 3D braided structure was constructed considering the braiding motion and using TEXGEN software (see Figure 2). Then, it was transferred to a finite element code (ABAQUS/implicit) to calculate the mechanical properties of the unit cell. In this calculation the yarns in the unit-cell were assumed to be solid constituents.

Figure 2. A basic unit cell of 3D braided structure (left: full model, right: quarter model)

After forming a basic unit cell, the thickness and shape of axial yarns were modified to model the multi-layered structure of the native cartilage. A numerical study was carried out to find a proper braided structure of which mechanical properties are close to those of the natural articular cartilage (see Figure 3)

Figure. 3. Finite element analysis of a unit cell of a braiding structure

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Biocompatible and biodegradable agarose and PLGA (Poly Lactic-co-Glycolic Acid) were used to manufacture a composite scaffold for regenerating articular cartilage. Agarose (SeaMatrix Agarose LE, Genosapiens) features high strength and low melting temperature.

Composite fabrication

Using the braiding parameters (the braiding angle and yarn thickness) calculated from the numerical analysis, rectangular 3D braided preforms were manufactured. Using VARTM (vacuum assisted resin transfer molding), the agarose gel was transferred to the braided preforms. Figure 4 shows the preform and its composites.

Figure 4. Braid preform for the composite scaffold and its composite with agarose gel

Mechanical characterization

The compressive behaviour of 3D braided composite scaffold was characterized using a UTM (Instron5565). A compressive load was applied to the scaffold in z direction (see Figure 2) at a rate of 0.1 mm/min. Before the compression test, a pre-load of 0.2-0.4 N was applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the finite element analysis, using ABAQUS, the constituent fiber (PLGA) and agarose gel were assumed as transversely isotropic and isotropic, respectively. The basic unit cell in Figure 2 was assumed to have the fiber volume fraction and the braiding of 60% and 45 degree, respectively. The circular cross-section was assumed for all yarns in the unit cell. The unit cell was then imported to ABAQUS for numerical analysis and meshed using tetra element (see Figure 5). The yarn was assumed transversely isotropic, so the material orientation for each yarn was set up as such. The mechanical properties of yarns were determined using the rule of mixture (PLGA fiber: agarose gel=80%:20%) [2, 3].

Figure 5. Finite element analysis of the unit cell. (a) material orientation set up, (b) boundary condition, (c) mesh

Firstly, the deformation behaviour of the unit cell was calculated when 1% uniform displacement was applied in one direction, e.g., to calculate the stiffness of the unit cell in x direction, 1% uniform displacement was imposed in that direction while other directions were left free. The tensile modulus of the unit cell were 0.659 MPa in both x and y direction, while compressive modulus on z direction is 1.010 MPa (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Tensile and compressive modulus of the unit cell.

This first results are promising because the moduli of the unit cell are close to that of natural cartilage (see Table 1), however its tensile modulus is low compared to that of natural cartilage. To design a 3D scaffold with the mechanical properties as close to those of natural one as possible, three parameters, i.e., yarn shape, braiding angle, and fiber volume fraction, were varied. The cross-section of yarns was also assumed to be elliptical one because the original solid yarns were forced during the braiding process and their cross-sections were changed accordingly. Braiding angles and fiber volume fractions were varied to 30, 45, and 60 degree and 30% and 45%, respectively (see Figure 7 for results). Note that the braiding angle and the fiber volume fraction are related quantities, so it is not possible to keep one variable unchanged while changing the other. In this study the yarn size was used to resolve this problem. For instance, the yarn size used for braids with a braiding angle of 45 degree was given thicker than those in braids with 60 degree braiding angle. The aspect ratio of yarns was fixed in all braids.

Figure 7. Influence of fiber volume fraction and Braiding angle for modulus
(Left: linear fit $R^2=0.9758$, right; $R^2=0.9484$)

Since the compressive modulus of native cartilage was reported in a range of 0.4 – 0.8 [5], 30-45% volume fraction and 30-45 degree braiding angles seems enough to mimic the natural cartilage. Among these, 30% and 30 degree were arbitrary chosen in this study for fiber volume fraction and braiding angle, respectively. Then, the tensile modulus was tailored by introducing the axial yarns. Here straight and elliptical yarns were added in the unit cell (see Figure 8 and 9). Then, the effect of the axial yarns on the tensile modulus was investigated by varying their volume fraction from 1 to 4% (see Figure 10).

Figure 8. Axial yarns introduced in the braided structure.

Figure 9. Numerical analysis of the unit cell with axial yarns (a) mesh, (b) load distribution when 1% elongation was imposed in y direction

Figure 10. Tensile modulus according to axial yarn volume fraction (Linear fit $R^2=0.999$)

Natural articular cartilage is a gradient structure, i.e., its mechanical properties vary in the tangential, transitional, and radial zone and the end plate on Figure 1 (it is also called superficial, intermediate, deep zone and calcified cartilage zone). Accordingly the unit cell was designed to have four different regions in the mechanical properties by varying the distribution of axial yarns to mimic them and using the data in Figure 10. Since the end plate has lowest modulus and strength in the tensile properties, so the end plate in the unit cell was given no axial yarn. Different fiber volume fractions of axial yarns, i.e., 1, 2, and 4% were given to the radial, transitional, and tangential zones, respectively. The optimum structure was set up as shown in Figure 11. The final results of the optimized unit cell are compared in Table 1, showing that the current design mimics the articular cartilage within reasonable error. In addition, though not discussed in detail, the anisotropic tensile properties were also obtained due to the braided structure. The ratio of tensile modulus in x direction to y direction was 1.92:1.26 without axial yarn.

Figure 11. Optimum structure of 3D braided composite for scaffold application

Table 1. Mechanical properties of optimum 3D braided composite scaffold.

	Compression (Young's)	Tensile			
		End plate	Radial	Transitional	Tangential
Theoretical composite modulus (MPa)	0.581	1.407	10.494	19.797	37.925
Native cartilage(MPa)	0.4 – 0.8 [5]	1-35 (knee) [4, 5]			

Next the validity of the current 3D braided scaffold design was investigated by measuring the mechanical behaviour of rectangular braided preform fabricated using the determined design parameters (see Figure 12). The 3D composite scaffold shows the bilinear stress and strain behaviour (similar to that of native cartilage in [6, 7]). The

initial modulus was 0.073 MPa from 0% to 12% strain, while the mid modulus was 0.259 MPa. These moduli are much lower than the theoretical value in Table, which may be due to the different yarn size used in the numerical model and experimental. The detailed discussion will be made at the conference.

Figure 12. Compression test of the braid composite scaffold

SUMMARY

The braiding technology is a viable process of manufacturing various kinds of composite preforms with tailored mechanical properties. In this study, we explored its feasibility of producing three-dimensional scaffold for regenerating articular cartilage. Utilizing the unit cell modeling of braided structures and importing it to finite element analysis, it was tentatively concluded that a three dimensional scaffold via the braiding technology could be manufactured successfully such that its mechanical properties match those of the natural cartilage and thus it can cultivate the cells (chondrocytes) leading the regeneration of the cartilage. The cell growth on it is in progress and will be reported at the conference.

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